

Fresh Eyes on CMIP Steering Group Terms of Reference

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This document complies with the [WCRP Guidelines on Membership and Responsibilities](#) and ensures that the Fresh Eyes on CMIP Steering Group has in place transparent, accountable, and effective procedures which honour the commitment and contribution of volunteering individuals, and ensure fairness, inclusion, and equity. Should the WCRP and/or Earth System Modelling and Observations (ESMO) Core Project guidelines change, this document will be updated.

Definitions

- **Fresh Eyes Directory** – The entry point for Fresh Eyes on CMIP. Members join the Directory via a sign up form and receive invites such as to projects, events, and consultations.
- **Fresh Eyes Projects** – The more engaged level of Fresh Eyes on CMIP. Projects members sign up and contribute to one or more active projects. Each project is overseen by one or more co-lead(s).
- **Fresh Eyes on CMIP Steering Group** – the group which oversees all Fresh Eyes activities, makes decisions on Fresh Eyes activities, and represents Fresh Eyes.
- **Body** – Body to whom the ToRs apply, the Fresh Eyes on CMIP Steering Group.
- **Wider Steering Group** – The Body members plus Fresh Eyes Projects co-leads
- **Parent Body (PB)** – the CMIP Panel is the Parent Body of the Fresh Eyes on CMIP Steering Group, to whom the Body immediately reports to.
- **Parent Body Liaison Member (PBLM)** – member of the CMIP Panel appointed as key liaison point to perform specified duties set out in the ToR. If that member is unable to carry out duties, the CMIP Panel can appoint a temporary replacement or replace the member holding this position.
- **Project** – a group of people temporarily working together to accomplish a specific task/set of tasks within the planned programme of work of a Body. Once that work is completed, the Project is closed.
- **Ex-officio member** – member of the Body by virtue of occupying an existing position within another organisation/body of importance or relevance to the Body. An ex-officio member is someone who holds a relevant position within a relevant committee/body/organisation. The membership position is assigned to the individual holding the office. Their membership ceases when they cease to hold that office. Their successor becomes the replacement ex-officio member.
- **Emeritus member** – a member who has reached their term limit/is no longer in employment but is invited to stay on the Body in an advisory capacity.
- **Conflict of interest:** A “conflict of interest” refers to any current professional, financial or other interest which could: i) significantly impair the individual’s objectivity in carrying out duties and responsibilities for the [Body], or ii) create an unfair advantage for any person or organisation.

For the purposes of this policy, circumstances that could lead a reasonable person to question an individual's objectivity, or whether an unfair advantage has been created, constitute a potential conflict of interest. These potential conflicts are subject to disclosure. [as defined by the IPCC in their [Conflict of Interest Policy](#)]

Purpose

1. The Fresh Eyes on CMIP Steering Group is a task team of the CMIP Panel, which is a panel of the Working Group on Coupled Modelling (WGCM), who in turn are a Working Group of the ESMO Core Project of WCRP. The Fresh Eyes on CMIP Steering Group is supported by the CMIP International Project Office.
2. The Fresh Eyes on CMIP Steering Group was initiated in 2023.
3. Goal of the Fresh Eyes on CMIP Steering Group: The Fresh Eyes on CMIP Steering Group is CMIP Panel task team charged with overseeing the activities and Projects of Fresh Eyes on CMIP.
4. Objectives of the Body:
 - 4.1. The Steering Group will brief the CMIP Panel and the WCRP ESMO Infrastructure Panel (WIP) and their relevant Task Teams, as well as other relevant WCRP committees and panels on progress, status, and plans for activities overseen by the Steering Group.
 - 4.2. The Steering Group works to empower early career scientists, researchers, and practitioners to meaningfully contribute to the objectives of the CMIP Panel and WGCM Infrastructure Panel and their relevant task teams.
 - 4.3. Coordinate activities across Fresh Eyes on CMIP: Reviewing project proposals, ensuring outcomes are Specific, Measurable, Achievable, Relevant, and Time-bound (SMART) and that project will have impact for its members
 - 4.4. The Steering Group works closely with the both the CMIP Panel and WIP , which coordinate the experimental design for CMIP and infrastructure support for CMIP respectively.

Below this point, except for (26), no need to change anything unless the Body has a specific cause to change them. Bodies are, of course, empowered to change these rules by a vote plus ESMO approval.

Term

5. The Fresh Eyes on CMIP Steering Group remains active until a decision is made to close it by the CMIP Panel.

Membership

TYPES & DECISION MAKING

6. There are three types of members: Full members, Ex-officio members and Emeritus members. All Full members must be affiliated with an organisation/institution or self-employed in a relevant field.
7. Only Full members are eligible to vote.
 - 7.1. Full members of Steering Group will:
 - a. have regard to the [ESMO Conflict of Interest Policy](#) and disclose any conflicts using the [ESMO Conflict of Interest form](#).
 - b. review before each meeting, where decisions and/or recommendations are being made, whether there are any interests which may conflict with their duties as members of the CMIP Panel and, if so, disclose them to the co-chairs and supporting CMIP IPO staff
 - c. be asked by the Co-chairs of Steering Group at each meeting where decisions and/or recommendations are being made to confirm they have carried out such a review and made such disclosure
 - d. not participate in any activity of Fresh Eyes on CMIP in relation to which they believe they have a conflict or possible conflict of interest without the consent of the Steering Group Co-chairs and CMIP IPO, who will manage the conflict in accordance with the Best Practice Note.
8. Decision making is by consensus. However, if this is not possible, a vote should be taken. For a decision to be approved, there must be a 2/3 majority vote with 75% quorum of Full Members.
9. The Parent Body (CMIP Panel) should be notified of any significant decisions within the annual report (see 34).

SIZE and ELIGIBILITY

10. Membership consists of at least two and at most three scientific co-chairs, at least two and at most three technical co-chairs, and a minimum of six and a maximum of twelve members, including the Full members and co-chairs. Emeritus members and ex-officio members can be appointed if needed. Emeritus and ex-officio members do not count within the maximum member number.
11. Across all Full members and co-chairs, there should be balanced regional representation, with at least one regional representative from the following six regions: Africa, Asia, Europe, Oceania, North America, Central and South America.
 - 11.1. Members can act as a regional representative if they have worked and maintain significant collaborations in the relevant region during their doctoral studies, post-doctoral work or other relevant working experience.
12. Co-chairs should not act as Project co-leads, except in exceptional circumstances. In such circumstances, a discussion among all co-chairs and the IPO should be held to assess their workload management.
13. Across the science and technical co-chairs, there should always be minimum one co-chair representing each of the Global North and Global South¹.
14. Members of the Steering Group must fit the ECR definition² on selection, but may fall outside the definition during their term.

¹ The Global South here is defined as countries in the Group of 77: <https://www.g77.org/doc/members.html>. Global North is defined as all other countries.

² Early career researchers (ECRs) are scientists, researchers, and practitioners in the early stages of their career. We definition this period as within seven years of obtaining their highest degree (excluding career breaks).

TERM, TERMINATION & EXTENSION

15. All appointments are initially for an initial term of two years, with up to two one-year extensions possible. A recommitment should be obtained from all members annually.
16. The two-year terms of the co-chairs shall be staggered by at least one calendar year as far as possible to prevent gaps in leadership and enhance resilience.
 - 16.1. When an existing member moves up to one of the co-chair positions, the appointment length “clock” is reset, with the condition that the member can serve on the committee up to a maximum of eight years altogether. Only in rare circumstances (which would require CMIP Panel approval) would any individual serve on the same committee for longer than eight years. Permission to do so must be sought from the CMIP Panel co-chairs using the form in Annex B.
 - 16.2. For an outgoing chair or co-chair, an extension of up to 1 year as a full member is possible, where a handover period is deemed necessary concurrently with the first year of a successor co-chair.
 - 16.3. Outgoing chairs/co-chairs, along with any other members who have exceeded their term, can be made *Emeritus members* at the discretion of the current co-chairs and CMIP Panel.
17. Emeritus members have their membership reviewed annually, there is no limit on this term.
18. The relevance of Ex-Officio membership is reviewed every two years.
19. All members can resign from their position at any point and are encouraged to give three months’ notice. Resigning members are encouraged to first discuss their circumstances with a chair/co-chairs. It might be more suitable to pause the membership in circumstances where ability to participate is restricted for a specific period (e.g., parental leave), or change the membership type. A membership pause is excluded from the service calculation in 14.1.
 - 19.1. Membership pause for parental leave will be automatically granted on notification to the CMIP International Project Office and Co-chairs. Leave from the Steering Group is permitted for up to 12 months for parental leave.
20. Unproductive members may be removed by the CMIP Panel co-chairs if any of the following criteria are met:
 - 20.1. Two unexcused Steering Group meetings within a 12-month period.
 - 20.2. Violation of the [WCRP code of conduct](#).
 - 20.3. Undeclared conflict of interest.
 - 20.4. No response following annual commitment request (response will be requested within 3-weeks, unless the member has informed the co-chairs or IPO that they are on leave, via email or automatic email Out of Office.)
21. All member removals, including the reasoning for the removal and a copy of the removal communication, must be shared with the CMIP Panel and CMIP IPO.

MEMBER APPOINTMENT

22. Co-chairs, Full and Emeritus members are appointed based on their personal experience and expertise and should be willing to represent relevant geographical or specialist science/technical areas, beyond their existing affiliations, as set out in the membership call text and table of Body members (25).
23. All new appointments should be made with consideration of compliance with the [WCRP Guidelines on Membership and Responsibilities](#) on diversity. Restrictions may be included to address under-representation within the Body. An open call should be issued by the CMIP IPO with a specification of requirements in line with membership responsibilities set by the co-chairs. The open call should run for at least a month. A deadline will be set for applications, which will be collected by the CMIP IPO. The CMIP IPO will coordinate all open calls for all CMIP bodies, which can be requested through standard reporting mechanisms or by special need.
24. All applications should contain as a minimum:
 - a. A statement (up to 500 words) demonstrating why they are a good candidate for that position
 - b. A 1 page Curriculum Vitae (CV)
25. For Full member positions, the applications will be collected by the CMIP IPO and issued to the selection committee to make a decision. Decision options are Appoint, Waitlist and Reject. Applicants should be excluded from any selection committees/votes relating to this process.
 - 25.1. For Full members positions, the co-chairs are responsible for the selection, alongside the CMIP Panel liaison member. A shortlist of minimum two candidates and maximum three candidates should be provided in priority order from 1 (with 1 being the first choice). The length of the shortlist can be extended if several positions are available. The CMIP Panel liaison member either approves or proposes a new ranking until agreement with the Fresh Eyes Steering Group co-chairs is reached. If a Co-chair is unable to join the selection group, they may delegate the responsibility to another Steering Group Full Member.
 - 25.2. For Chair/Co-chair positions, the current co-chairs are responsible for the selection. A shortlist of maximum three candidates should be provided in priority order from 1 (with 1 being the first choice). The CMIP Panel liaison either approves or propose a new ranking until agreement with the co-chairs is reached.
 - 25.3. For all positions, the selection committee should evaluate whether the candidate's experience makes them suitable for the role, including suitability for the role of regional representative.
26. Members involved in shortlisting can refer to the CMIP Panel, for arbitration.
27. No communication to candidates can take place until CMIP Panel liaison member approval has been obtained.

Roles and Responsibilities

28. It is the responsibility of all members to ensure the activities of the Fresh Eyes on CMIP Steering Group are in accordance with the Goal and objectives set out in (3) and (4).

29. It is the responsibility of all members to ensure the CMIP IPO supporting their activity has up to date contact details for them and is notified of any changes to role and employing institution.
30. Co-chairs are responsible for reviewing the table of member types every two years. Any amendments to the table should be issued as a new version of this ToR (51).

25a. TABLE: MEMBER TYPES OF FRESH EYES ON CMIP STEERING GROUP, limited to 6-12 Full Members by (8)

Member type	Appointment process	Term	Responsibilities /Justification
Scientific co-chairs (2-3)	Community nominations (including self-nomination)	2+1+1 years	<p>The scientific co-chairs' roles are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. To provide leadership of the Steering Group and vision and drive to achieve the Steering Group's aims and objectives. b. To chair meetings of the Steering Group. c. To ensure coordination of and liaison between Projects, with the support of the IPO. d. To ensure coordination and collaboration between Projects and other CMIP Task Teams, with the support of the IPO e. To liaise with the CMIP Panel co-chairs and provide guidance to the CMIP IPO regarding project priorities. f. To represent Fresh Eyes in CMIP Extended Panel meetings. g. To actively promote the work of Fresh Eyes on CMIP. h. To report, as relevant, to the CMIP Panel, WIP, and other relevant WCRP activities.
Technical co-chairs (2-3)	Community nominations (including self-nomination)	2+1+1 years	<p>The technical co-chairs' roles are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. To provide leadership of the Steering Group and vision and drive to achieve the Steering Group's aims and objectives. b. To chair meetings of the Steering Group. c. To ensure coordination of and liaison between Projects, with the support of the IPO. a. To liaise with the WIP co-chairs and provide guidance to the CMIP IPO regarding project priorities. a. To represent Fresh Eyes in WIP Extended Panel meetings

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. To actively promote the work of Fresh Eyes on CMIP. b. To report, as relevant, to the CMIP Panel, WIP, and other relevant WCRP activities.
Full members – Core Panel (up to 6 plus co-chairs)	Open Call	2+1+1 years	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Attend and contribute to Wider Steering Group meetings, typically meetings every two months, to drive progress and review issues and risks arising Fresh Eyes on CMIP. Additional meetings of the Steering Group may be called as needed. b. Work with other Steering Group members to develop white papers and other publications as relevant and to support Fresh Eyes development and impact. c. Ensure adequate availability to be able to respond to requests for support from Steering Group co-chairs and the IPO. d. Promote the work of Fresh Eyes and CMIP within their own networks and wider community. e. Commit to promoting diversity, equality, inclusivity, and environmental sustainability within the CMIP project. f. Steering Group members will assist the co-chairs with delivering the objectives of the Steering Group and liaison with Projects.
Ex-officio (1)	CMIP Panel Liaison Member	Reviewed every two years	<p>Provide linkage to CMIP Panel</p> <p>To ensure coordination and collaboration between Projects and other CMIP Task Teams, with the support of the IPO</p>
Emeritus (2)	Body & PBLM (annual review)	One year, annually renewed	Provide historical knowledge and experienced insight
Ex-officio (1)	Fresh Eyes Platform rep	One year, Reviewed annually	Responsible for platform monitoring and maintenance (if significant maintenance is required, this member can lead a relevant new project)

25b. TABLE: MEMBER TYPES OF WIDER STEERING GROUP, a subsidiary of the STEERING GROUP

Fresh Eyes on CMIP Project co-leads	Open Call	Project lifetime (reviewed every two years)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Report on areas of responsibility, provide relevant material to support Steering Group decision making, and adopt actions as needed. b. Develop and deliver white papers and other publications as relevant to the goals and activities of the Project, as relevant, outlined in the Project objectives. c. Manage risks relevant to specific tasks of the Project in close coordination with the Steering Group and IPO. d. Project Co-leads attendance at Wider Steering Group meetings is welcomed but remains optional, unless a project updates roundtable is scheduled. In this case, a project co-lead should join the meeting if possible. If no co-lead can join, an alternative update process will be available.
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Meetings and deliverables

31. The Wider Steering Group shall meet virtually or in person on at least a quarterly basis with additional meetings as required e.g., meetings will typically be held every two months. Increased meetings may be necessary in periods of high activity.
32. Meetings will be organised by the CMIP IPO and chaired by one of the co-chairs. The CMIP IPO will provide the secretariat function for any Steering Group meetings in accordance with (35).
33. CMIP meetings and events shall be professional, respectful, and harassment-free environments for all participants in line with the [WCRP code of conduct](#).
34. The majority of Steering Group meetings will be held virtually with in-person meetings arranged if required and with due consideration of carbon impact. Meeting timings will be rotated as far as possible to ensure members in certain time zones are not disadvantaged. If possible, the Steering Group will try hold one hybrid meeting every two-years. The meeting should be held at a workshop, conference, or other event, that multiple Steering Group members plan to attend.
35. The agenda will be developed by the IPO and co-chairs and circulated to Steering Group members in advance of any meeting. Meeting papers should be circulated at least three working days in advance.
36. Meeting formats will reflect the nature of, and topics for, discussion and may include small group breakout sessions.
37. Non-members may be invited to present or contribute to Steering Group meetings.
38. An annual report will be supplied to the WGCM in the format and timeframe requested by them, in line with JSC reporting requirements. This will set out the achievements, significant decisions and recommendations, issues, plans, membership, and financial requests for the next 2 years and updates on Subsidiary Bodies.

Publications

39. All official publications of any activity within CMIP, except for those controlled by the ESMO IPO, or academic or professional publishers, must be published by the CMIP IPO. Where the CMIP IPO has delegated the publication to another IPO, the CMIP IPO must have sight of the final version prior to publication. Publications co-authored by members as part of the Fresh Eyes on CMIP goals and objectives published by an ordinary peer-reviewing publisher should be provided to the CMIP IPO and included in the annual report.

Code of conduct

40. All activities of the Fresh Eyes on CMIP Steering Group and Wider Steering Group, and its representations on behalf of it by its members and members of its subsidiary bodies, must be made in compliance with the [WCRP Code of Conduct](#).

Subsidiary Bodies

A list of all Projects of the Fresh Eyes on CMIP group can be found at: <https://bit.ly/fresh-eyes-projects-all>

PROJECTS

41. A Project may be proposed by the Steering Group, CMIP International Project Office, CMIP Panel, WGCM Infrastructure Panel, Task Team, or any Fresh Eyes on CMIP Directory member.
42. Proposals for Projects should be submitted to the Steering Group for approval prior to initiation. Following Steering Group approval, the Project should also receive approval from the CMIP Panel prior to initiation. It is anticipated that approval will be granted within 30 working days of receipt of Notification.
43. Each Project should have at least two co-leads appointed for resilience before approval. Project proposals can either a) nominate co-leads on proposal, or b) request an open call for project co-leads is held across existing Fresh Eyes Directory members.
44. A list of Project members should be held by the co-chairs and the supporting project office.
45. Project activities must comply with the CMIP Panel's, WIP's, and/or Fresh Eyes on CMIP's Terms of Reference. Namely, Projects should comply with the overarching objectives of CMIP. The Fresh Eyes Steering Group Full Members are responsible for this compliance.
46. If a Project has delivered on the objectives outlined in the proposal, the team will be closed, and letters of thanks will be issued from the Steering Group co-chairs to the Task Team members in recognition of their contribution. Requests for extensions or changes to Project objectives will be reviewed by the Steering Group.
47. Should a Project be unable to progress delivery of the planned objectives or adjudication be required, the co-leads must report this to the Steering Group co-chairs.
48. CMIP Panel liaison and Steering Group co-chairs will encourage CMIP Task Teams to contribute to Projects as needed/requested.

Amendments to the ToR

49. Any recommendations for amendments to the Terms of Reference should be submitted to the CMIP Panel for approval. This should include a cover table, using this template, providing a summary of the changes from the approved ToRs:

Page# Section Title, Clause #	Change Description	Rationale/Justification

VERSION RECORD

Version number	Approval body	Date approved
Version 1.0	CMIP Core Panel	
Version 1.1		

ANNEX A

Fresh Eyes on CMIP Project proposal template

This template is copy of the contents of this form bit.ly/propose-a-Fresh-Eyes-project which must be completed and submitted to cmip-ipo@esa.int

1. Project title

2. Project abstract

3. Project objectives/goals (these should be SMART goals)

4. Planned duration of project (months)

5. Related CMIP Task Teams

6. Project co-leads

7. Is this project open for new members to join?

8. Do you need access to OnlyOffice for this project?

9. Project proposer name and email

ANNEX B

This template is copy of the contents of this form <https://bit.ly/ESMO-Nomination-Form> which must be completed and submitted.

Nomination for [Appointment/Extension]

Nominated for: [Name of the WCRP high-level steering committee]

As: [role of the nominated person, e.g., co-chair, member...]

1. DETAILS OF CANDIDATE NOMINATED

- Title:
- First Name:
- Last Name:
- Year of PhD (or the final academic degree) obtained:
- Nationality (citizenship):
- Residing country:
- Affiliation:
- E-mail Address:

2. MEMBER SINCE & UNTIL (year, in case of extension)

- Expertise vis-à-vis the role of the [WCRP core activity] (maximum of 8 lines):
- Science Background (maximum of 8 lines):
- Positions held (maximum of 8 lines):
- Five most relevant publications
- Why is this individual particularly suited to this [steering committee]? (maximum of 5 lines)

3. SUBMITTED BY

- Title:
- First Name:
- Last Name:
- Organisation: